

Trust and Risk-aware Human–AI Collaboration Framework in AI-Enabled OT Systems

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Abstract—Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into Operational Technology (OT) and Cyber Physical Systems (CPS), offering enhanced automation and predictive capabilities. However, this integration introduces new risks, including loss of human control, degraded trust, and vulnerabilities to adversarial threats. Existing frameworks either focus on technical safety or human factors, and lack actionable mechanisms linking trust, control, and cybersecurity in OT environments. This paper bridges the gaps by proposing a control-theoretic framework for human-AI collaboration that is risk-aware, trust-sensitive, and aligned with formal governance standards. We illustrate the workings of the proposed framework by applying it to a realistic case study. The results provide valuable insight into Human-AI collaboration in terms of control authority and responsibility and the applicability of the proposed method in critical safety systems. The proposed framework not only manages the Human-AI collaboration during system operation but also makes sure that AI integration to the system complies with updated requirements.

Index Terms—Trustworthy AI, Human-AI collaboration, Human-Centric AI, Human-Centered AI (HCAI), Operational Technology (OT), Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), Control sharing, Cyber security, Control theory

I. INTRODUCTION

Operational Technology (OT) systems in Critical Infrastructures (CIs) and Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) increasingly integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance automation, efficiency, and predictive capabilities. While digital transformation initiatives accelerate this trend [1], the integration of AI into OT environments introduces significant challenges. Unlike other domains, failures in OT can directly impact physical safety, service reliability, and societal well-being. Therefore, AI adoption in such contexts requires particular caution regarding safety, security, trust, compliance, and resilience to adversarial threats. The NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) [2] highlights risk management as essential for the responsible development and deployment of AI systems. Beyond technical risks, the opaque nature of AI systems creates uncertainty due to unseen or unpredictable threats, particularly in CIs where interdependent subsystems may react unexpectedly under stress [3]. The adoption of AI compounds this uncertainty, making system behavior less predictable and increasing the likelihood of cascading failures. Furthermore,

accountability for unintended consequences of AI-driven decisions is still an open question, which is highly crucial in CPS/OT, as failures in OT may result not only in financial loss but also in threats to human life. Recent regulatory initiatives, including the EU AI Act, ISO/IEC 24029-1 for AI risk management, ISO/IEC TR 5469:2024 for functional safety, DHS AI in Critical Infrastructure, and CISA’s AI Roadmap, reflect the global urgency for safe, secure, and human-aligned AI deployment in critical domains. Human involvement remains central to CPS and OT operations, particularly as autonomy increases. The Industry 5.0 paradigm reinforces this by shifting focus from full automation toward human-centric collaboration [4], aligning with the Defense-in-Depth principle that stresses the integration of people, processes, and technology. However, the growing complexity and opacity of AI can erode human operators’ situational awareness, diminish their observability of system behaviour, and reduce their control authority. These factors create trust degradation and authority misalignment, which may lead to unsafe or non-compliant behavior if left unaddressed. Moreover, traditional risk assessment and threat modeling frameworks often overlook the human as an active agent in the control loop. This disjointed treatment of human and AI roles leads to design blind spots where trust, resilience, and accountability are not adequately modeled. Control theory provides strong tools for analyzing system behavior via observability and controllability, while human–AI interaction research highlights how trust dynamics influence reliance on automation. Governance frameworks (e.g., NIST AI RMF) emphasize trustworthy and auditable AI but lack actionable mechanisms for adaptive control sharing. These domains remain disconnected, leaving a critical gap in designing AI-enabled OT systems that are both safe and trustworthy.

This paper bridges that gap by proposing a control-theoretic framework that models humans and AI as co-controllers with distinct observability and controllability profiles. The framework offers an approach to evaluate AI integration, jointly addressing risk, trust, and control, while aligning with AI governance standards. It also introduces a conceptual trust-mode model to reason about authority sharing, trust calibration, and recovery, providing a foundation for safer, transparent, and accountable human–AI collaboration in critical infrastructure.

Our contribution is threefold:

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- A control-theoretic design framework for human–AI collaboration in CPS/OT systems, modeling humans and AI as co-controllers with distinct controllability profiles.
- A conceptual trust-state model that supports reasoning about trust calibration, loss, and recovery to guide authority-sharing design decisions.
- A governance-aligned methodology, integrated with the NIST AI Risk Management Framework, to help system designers evaluate AI integration from a cybersecurity, trust, and control perspective.

II. RELATED WORK

Prior research in Human-in-the-Loop CPS (HiLCPS) has explored frameworks for determining when and how human operators should be involved in automated systems. Gil et al. [5] propose a situational-awareness-driven framework to guide human involvement, while Schirner et al. [6] emphasize the need to formally model human limitations. Eraslan et al. [7] studied shared control between pilot and autopilot in presence of anomalies and leveraged the notion of Capacity for Maneuver (CfM) to define the conditions under which pilots should regain control from autopilots, highlighting the need for dynamic role reallocation based on system stress.

Multiple works model trust as a continuous or latent state variable using linear dynamical systems (LDS), Markov Decision Processes (MDP), Partially Observable MDPs (POMDPs), or time-driven differential equations, mainly in robotics and collaborative manufacturing setups. Trust dynamics inform authority allocation, assistance-seeking, task assignment, and supervision/interruption policies in human–AI teams, enhancing adaptation and performance. From the control-theoretic perspective, trust has been integrated as a decision or optimization variable in frameworks such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) [8] and POMDP-based collaboration models [9]. Recent research also explores meta-planning with explicit trust reasoning [10] and optimization of robot behavior to improve operator confidence [11], but these works focus on user experience rather than on cybersecurity or system resilience. Zeynep [12] proposed the HAIG framework for analyzing evolving trust dynamics with a trust-utility orientation, rather than a risk-based approach, aiming to maintain appropriate trust levels over time.

In parallel, some studies address mutual trust estimation [13], [14] and Cyber-Physical-Human (CPH) architectures [13], but these lack formal trust-by-design methods and runtime synthesis of trust-safe control. Observability and controllability, core control-theoretic properties essential to system safety [15], have been extended in CPS to address fault detection, resilient control, and adversarial state estimation [16], yet typically treat humans as external observers rather than co-controllers with distinct observability and controllability. Shared control and mixed-initiative systems have introduced intent recognition and authority-sharing [17], [18], but without formal mechanisms linking operator trust and system risk.

In human–AI interaction, numerous studies show how transparency, confidence calibration, and workload influence trust,

and that both overtrust and distrust impair performance [19]–[21]. Dynamic models like VIRTISI map trust evolution across discrete states (distrust, recovery, overtrust) [22], yet they are not integrated into real-time control for CPS/OT environments. Other approaches, such as Pfister et al. [23], incorporate human values in runtime monitoring of CPS but do not address authority-sharing under risk.

Governance frameworks, including the EU AI Act [24] and NIST AI Risk Management Framework [1], highlight human oversight as a key requirement, emphasizing that humans must remain in control through appropriate measures. However, these frameworks are mostly high-level and focus on ethics or compliance, offering limited technical guidance on applying AI safely in CPSs where humans, cyber, and physical components interact. The EU AI Act also warns that increasing AI autonomy may reduce human intervention, potentially compromising safety [25].

In summary, although significant progress has been made in control safety, trust modeling, human–AI collaboration, and governance, there is no unified, standards-aligned strategy covering these aspect in OT/CPS environment. This paper addresses this gap by proposing a trust and risk-aware Human–AI collaboration framework.

III. METHOD

In this section, we present our proposed method for enabling trustworthy and human-centered AI collaboration in CPS and OT environments. Our framework is structured according to the four high-level functions of the NIST AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) — Map, Measure, Manage, and Govern — to responsibly support trustworthy AI development and dynamic risk-aware adaptation. Our proposed Trust and Risk-Aware Human–AI Collaboration (TRA-HIC) framework complies with the human centrality requirement emphasized in Responsible AI guidelines [26]. Characteristics of trustworthy AI in CPS, including validity, reliability, safety, security, resilience, accountability, transparency, explainability, and interpretability, are also considered in the design of our framework to enhance its applicability. Inspired by control theory, a well-established modeling approach for OT systems, and trust modeling, we represent human and AI roles as co-controllers and evaluate system-level trustworthiness and risk.

A. Background: Control-Theoretic Modeling of CPS

Cyber-Physical Systems are often modeled using control theory, where the system (plant) dynamics are described via state-space equations. A typical feedback control loop includes (see Figure 1):

- Plant: The physical system being controlled
- Controller: Issues commands to drive the system to desired behaviour
- Sensors: Measure system outputs
- Actuators: Apply control inputs to the plant

The system dynamics are captured as:

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t), \quad y(t) = Cx(t) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Plant

Where $x(t)$ is the system state vector, $u(t)$ is the control input, $y(t)$ is the observed output, A is the system dynamics matrix, B is the input matrix, and C is the output matrix. Controllability and observability are essential properties in control theory that determine whether a system can be effectively steered and monitored. A system is controllable if its internal states can be driven to any desired state using control input $u(t)$, and observable if its internal states can be inferred from the output $y(t)$. Controllability and observability are evaluated using the Kalman rank condition. A system is controllable if the controllability matrix shown in Equation (2) has full rank $\text{rank}(Q_c) = n$. And it is observable if the observability matrix shown in Equation (3) also has full rank $\text{rank}(Q_o) = n$, where n is the number of system states.

$$Q_c = [B \quad AB \quad A^2B \quad \dots \quad A^{n-1}B] \quad (2)$$

$$Q_o = \begin{bmatrix} C \\ CA \\ CA^2 \\ \vdots \\ CA^{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

B. Trust and Risk-Aware Human-AI Collaboration (TRA-HIC) Framework

In the following, we explain each of the four stages of the TRA-HIC framework in detail. An overview of the framework is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Trust and Risk-Aware Human-AI Collaboration framework

1) **MAP: Modeling Human and AI Roles in CPS:** Based on the control-theoretic background introduced earlier, this step models the distinct roles of the human agent and the AI agent in the system. Unlike traditional system modeling approaches, we explicitly include the human operator as part of the control loop. Both human agent and AI agent are treated as co-controllers, each capable of applying control inputs and perceiving system outputs. Accordingly, we define separate control inputs and observable outputs for both agents, as well as individual controllability and observability properties. This approach enables the analysis and comparison of each agent's influence and perception capacity under different human-AI collaboration approaches, such as human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, supervisory control, AI-in-the-loop, and other configurations that will be discussed later. In addition, it sets the foundation for evaluating how control authority and information access affect system behavior, trust calibration, and risk mitigation across varying operational scenarios. To this end, the MAP step establishes the foundational structure of the CPS and extends the classical control formulation to include distinct control and observation pathways for each agent. We treat both the human operator and the AI system as co-controllers of the CPS, each with their own observability and controllability profiles. Building on Equation (1), the system dynamics are extended to incorporate both human and AI agents as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= Ax(t) + B_H U_H(t) + B_{AI} U_{AI}(t) \\ y_i(t) &= C_i x(t) \quad i \in \{H, AI\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $x(t)$ is the system state; $U_H(t)$ and $U_{AI}(t)$ are the control inputs from the human and AI agents, respectively; $y_H(t)$ and $y_{AI}(t)$ are the perceived outputs by the human and AI agents. The system has two sets of controllability and observability parameters: O_H and C_H denote the observability and controllability for the human, while O_{AI} and C_{AI} denote the observability and controllability for the AI. A is the system dynamic matrix; B_H and B_{AI} are the input matrices defining control authority by the human and AI, respectively; C_H and C_{AI} are the output matrices defining the observability of the human and AI, respectively. A summary of the key parameters and variables is provided in Table II.

One can construct controllability and observability matrices, as explained in the background, for both the human and AI agents and evaluate their ranks to assess these properties. These matrices quantify each agent's visibility and influence over the system and are used in later steps to calibrate trust and assess risk. These properties determine the information access and decision power each agent has during normal and adversarial operations.

2) **MEASURE: Quantifying Trust and Risk:** This step focuses on assessing the operational state of the system by measuring *Trust function* ($T_H(t)$) and *Risk function* ($Risk(t)$) metrics. These metrics are dynamically computed and used in subsequent phases to guide control adaptation and ensure trustworthy AI operation.

The trust function measures the human’s trust in the AI agent. Recent work in the field of human factors has highlighted various factors that influence human–AI collaboration, such as human confidence, workload, and decision agreement [27]. Trustworthy AI guidelines also emphasize factors such as transparency and explainability that may affect trust level. Therefore, we consider three factors that combine insights from both the human–AI collaboration literature and trustworthy AI guidelines:

- 1) **Transparency (Tr)**: System transparency and explainability (aligned with transparency and interpretability)
- 2) **Agreement (Ag)**: Alignment between AI and human decisions (linked to alignment and reliability)
- 3) **Reliability (Re)**: Historical reliability of AI agents (reflecting past AI performance)

Moreover, trust is a dynamic factor that evolves during human-AI collaboration under different operational conditions. As a result, we define trust as a dynamic time-dependent value $T_H(t) \in [0, 1]$. Consequently, the trust function is calculated using the Equation (5). It is a weighted function where each input is normalized to $[0, 1]$, and the weights satisfy $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 1$ for simplicity.

$$T_H(t + 1) = \lambda_1 \cdot Tr(t) + \lambda_2 \cdot Ag(t) + \lambda_3 \cdot Re(t) \quad (5)$$

In this step, we compute the *Risk function* by combining control-theoretic indicators and system-level vulnerabilities. Risk is driven by deficits in *Observability* and *Controllability*, for instance, in the event of failures or incidents that hinder the human operator from perception or controlling the system effectively. It also incorporates an underlying *System Risk Score* ($R_{sys}(t)$), which captures safety, security, and resilience factors, as emphasized in the AI guidelines, and is particularly important in CPS and OT systems. This system risk score may vary due to hazards, cyber attacks, or other uncertainties and can be informed by a risk assessment process. Accordingly, the risk function measures the risk based on Equation (6):

$$\text{Risk}(t) = w_O(1 - \mathcal{O}_H(t)) + w_C(1 - \mathcal{C}_H(t)) + w_R R_{sys}(t) \quad (6)$$

This step provides quantitative indicators of operational risk and human-AI misalignment. For simplicity, the weights satisfy $w_O + w_C + w_R = 1$. Note that the weights used in Equations (5) and (6) can be adjusted by domain experts to reflect the characteristics of the OT system and its environment. Section IV provides further elaboration and explains in more detail how agreement and reliability can be computed quantitatively.

3) **MANAGE: Adaptive Control Redistribution**: The MANAGE phase focuses on dynamically adjusting the control authority between human agent and AI agent, based on real-time trust and risk indicators derived from the MEASURE step. This ensures that control shifts are both justifiable and aligned with safety, performance, and accountability requirements in CPS/OT environments. In particular, accountability, one of the core characteristics of trustworthy AI, is supported by explicit control attribution and the ability to adapt authority based on

measurable conditions. This step facilitates maintaining human oversight and responsible AI behavior in critical operations. Using the outputs of the Measure step, we implement real-time adjustment of control sharing between human and AI as follows:

$$u(t) = \alpha_H(t)u_H(t) + \alpha_{AI}(t)u_{AI}(t), \quad \alpha_H + \alpha_{AI} = 1 \quad (7)$$

Here, $\alpha_H(t) \in [0, 1]$ and $\alpha_{AI}(t) = 1 - \alpha_H(t)$ represent the control weights assigned to human and AI agents, respectively. These weights can dynamically update based on the output of the Measure step, trust function ($T_H(t)$) and risk function ($Risk(t)$), as well as observability ($\mathcal{O}_H(t)$) and controllability ($\mathcal{C}_H(t)$) scores. Leveraging these factors, we ensure that when:

- High trust and low risk \rightarrow control shifts toward AI ($\alpha_{AI}(t) = 1$)
- Low trust or high risk \rightarrow control returns to human ($\alpha_H(t) = 1$)
- Partial trust or degraded observability \rightarrow co-control (blended authority ($\alpha_H + \alpha_{AI} = 1$))

To be able to enforce this control redistribution, the trust threshold for safe delegation should be defined for each system as follows:

$$\alpha_{AI}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } T_H(t) < \tau_{min} \text{ OR } Risk(t) > \rho_{safe} \\ T_H(t) & \text{if } \tau_{min} \leq T_H(t) \leq \tau_{max} \text{ AND } Risk(t) < \rho_{safe} \\ 1 & \text{if } T_H(t) > \tau_{max} \text{ AND } Risk(t) < \rho_{safe} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here, τ_{min}, τ_{max} refers to soft thresholds for trust-based delegation that should be defined by the system owner/stackholder and ρ_{safe} is the risk bound under which AI can operate autonomously.

This adaptive delegation policy supports shared control in real time, prevents overtrust and automation complacency, and enables responsive action under degraded system states or anomalous AI behavior. Moreover, it operationalizes core trustworthy AI principles, particularly accountability, reliability, and safety, by coupling control authority with explicit trust and risk metrics. This ensures that AI autonomy is not only earned, but also continuously monitored and revocable in high-stakes CPS/OT environments.

4) **GOVERN: Trust State Classification and Compliance Support**: The GOVERN phase provides a supervisory layer to ensure that the human–AI collaboration process remains transparent, accountable, and aligned with trustworthy AI standards. Unlike the MEASURE and MANAGE steps, which affect runtime trust calibration and control sharing, this phase focuses on system-level oversight, traceability, and assurance.

Inspired by human factors research on trust calibration and operator behavior [19], we classify human–AI trust into a set of interpretable modes in this step. Previous studies on trust modes describe broad categories such as distrust, calibrated trust, and overtrust, however, we operationalize trust states quantitatively using sliding window metrics. This approach captures not only the level of trust but also its stability and

trend, enabling fine-grained governance monitoring. The trust modes are defined as:

- Not Trusted: low trust, either unstable or under hazardous conditions;
- Fully Trusted: stable and consistently high trust;
- Semi-Trusted (Steady): moderate trust that is stable;
- Semi-Trusted (Degrading): moderate trust that is decreasing;
- Semi-Trusted (Recovering): moderate trust that is increasing.

Rather than relying solely on a fixed trust value, we compute a *windowed mean trust* ($\mu_T(t)$), a *slope* ($s_T(t)$), and a *variance* $\sigma_T^2(t)$ to capture the level, trend, and stability of trust. The trust mode is calculated over a time window of length Δ , which reflects how trust evolves throughout system operation. As shown in Equation (9), $\mu_T(t)$ corresponds to the average trust score over the recent period and reflects the overall level of operator trust at time t :

$$\mu_T(t) = \frac{1}{\Delta} \sum_{i=t-\Delta+1}^t T_i \quad (9)$$

The slope metric $s_T(t)$ calculated based on Equation (10) indicates whether the trend of the trust score is steady, increasing, or decreasing. A positive slope indicates trust is recovering, whereas a negative slope signals degrading trust.

$$s_T(t) = \frac{T_t - T_{t-\Delta+1}}{\Delta} \quad (10)$$

Finally, the trust variance $\sigma_T^2(t)$ captures the observed fluctuation of the trust values within the observation window Δ as follow:

$$\sigma_T^2(t) = \frac{1}{\Delta - 1} \sum_{i=t-\Delta+1}^t (T_i - \mu_T)^2 \quad (11)$$

Low variance corresponds to stable trust, while high variance indicates unstable trust dynamics. Using these metrics, Equation (12) defines the trust modes.

The classification rules use domain-defined thresholds τ_L (low trust), τ_H (high trust), ϵ_s (slope sensitivity), and ϵ_v (variance threshold). These thresholds should be defined by domain experts based on the operational context. Additionally, the system risk score $R_{sys}(t)$ is incorporated to ensure that hazardous operating conditions are explicitly flagged, aligning with the fail-safe concept and enabling post-incident analysis.

These trust modes are not used directly to alter the control authority in the run time, rather, they act as governance markers to support higher-level oversight. They enable the system to log state transitions for audits and post-incident analysis, trigger UI or explanation adjustments, and support policy enforcement. Moreover, the integration of $R_{sys}(t)$ ensures that hazardous situations are identified even if control redistribution has already been handled by the MANAGE phase. The goal is to classify the state of human-to-AI trust into one of these trust modes to enhance traceability in human-AI interactions

and strengthen alignment with trustworthy AI principles, such as those defined in the NIST AI RMF, ISO 42001, and IEC 62443.

Finally, the GOVERN step integrates a feedback layer that maps the framework's outputs to the key dimensions of trustworthy AI. This allows for both runtime assessment and offline review of how the system satisfies high-level requirements. When deviations are detected in the GOVERN step, this feedback loop can prompt recalibration or compliance review. In this way, the GOVERN step ensures that the system not only adapts in real time but also remains auditable, justifiable, and aligned with responsible AI principles throughout its lifecycle.

Table I shows the alignment of the proposed framework with the characteristics of trustworthy AI.

IV. CASE STUDY

In this section, we evaluate our proposed framework using the classical two-tank water level control system, a widely referenced benchmark in industrial automation research. The system consists of two interconnected tanks with controllable inflow pumps and gravitational outflow, representing a common industrial process control scenario found in chemical plants, water treatment facilities, and manufacturing systems, representative of industrial OT environments. The system dynamics follow nonlinear differential equations and are linearized around the steady-state operating point. We use the benchmark model and parameter values published by MathWorks in their open-access example of two-tank system control ¹ and implement this model in MATLAB R2025a for the case study.

To demonstrate the human-AI collaboration, we assume that the system is collaboratively controlled by a human operator and an AI agent, both issuing commands based on their respective sensor readings. To evaluate our framework, we simulate an operational scenario where the system naturally transitions through multiple phases due to internal faults and external threats. This enables us to assess how control authority changes between the human and AI under different conditions, whether the trust mode correctly identifies these modes, and how it can further enhance system control in alignment with trustworthy AI requirements in OT environments.

The system operation begins in a normal state, then experiences a sensor fault affecting the perception of both agents (i.e., human and AI). This is followed by a recovery period. Later, a cyberattack degrades the AI's observability by injecting noise into its sensor data, while the human's perception remains accurate. Finally, the system enters a post-attack recovery phase. These events drive the system through five operational phases: Normal, Faulty, Recovery, Cyberattack, and Post-attack Recovery. Each of these phases offers an opportunity to observe how trust and risk evolve, and how control authority shifts between human and AI as a result. We simulate the system operation over 100 seconds, during

¹<https://se.mathworks.com/help/robust/ug/control-of-a-two-tank-system.html>

$$\text{Trust Mode}(t) = \begin{cases} \text{Fully Trusted,} & \mu_T(t) \geq \tau_H \text{ and } |s_T(t)| < \epsilon_s, \\ \text{Not Trusted,} & (\mu_T(t) \leq \tau_L \text{ and } |s_T(t)| < \epsilon_s \text{ and } \sigma_T^2(t) > \epsilon_v) \\ & \text{OR } (\mu_T(t) \leq \tau_L \text{ and } R_{sys}(t) \text{ is high and } s_T(t) < 0), \\ \text{Semi-Trusted (Steady),} & \tau_L < \mu_T(t) < \tau_H \text{ and } |s_T(t)| < \epsilon_s \text{ and } \sigma_T^2(t) < \epsilon_v, \\ \text{Semi-Trusted (Degrading),} & \tau_L < \mu_T(t) < \tau_H \text{ and } s_T(t) \leq -\epsilon_s, \\ \text{Semi-Trusted (Recovering),} & \tau_L < \mu_T(t) < \tau_H \text{ and } s_T(t) \geq \epsilon_s. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

TABLE I
ALIGNMENT OF TRA-HIC FRAMEWORK WITH TRUSTWORTHY AI CHARACTERISTICS

Trustworthy AI Property	Evaluated In	TRA-HIC Source
Valid and Reliable	MEASURE	Historical performance and agreement metrics
Safe, Secure and Resilient	MEASURE	Risk(t) function and R_{sys}
Accountable and Transparent	MANAGE	Delegation logic, control traceability
and Explainable and Interpretable	MEASURE / GOVERN	System transparency, trust modes

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF KEY PARAMETERS AND VARIABLES

Symbol	Description
$x(t)$	System state vector
$u(t)$	Control inputs
$y(t)$	Observed output
A	System dynamics matrix
B	Input matrix
C	Output matrix
$O(t), C(t)$	Observability and Controllability
$u_H(t), u_{AI}(t)$	Control inputs from human and AI agents
$y_H(t), y_{AI}(t)$	Outputs observed by human and AI agents
B_H, B_{AI}	Input matrices defining control authority
C_H, C_{AI}	Output matrices defining observability
Q_C, Q_O	Controllability and observability matrices
$T_H(t)$	Trust function at time t
$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$	Weights in trust computation
$\alpha_H(t), \alpha_{AI}(t)$	Control authority weights (human/AI)
τ_{min}, τ_{max}	Trust thresholds for delegation
$Risk(t)$	Computed system-level risk at time t
$R_{sys}(t)$	System risk score
w_O, w_C, w_R	Weights for observability, controllability, and risk
$O_H(t), C_H(t)$	Observability and controllability scores for human
ρ_{safe}	Risk threshold for safe AI delegation
$\Delta T_H(t)$	Trust gradient (trust change over time)

which the system transitions through five distinct operational phases, each phase spans approximately 20 seconds. Figure 3 shows Tank 1 and Tank 2 behaviour across different system operations.

Table III summarizes the five operational phases considered in the simulation. For each phase, the table specifies the noise levels added to the AI and human sensor measurements, as well as the corresponding system risk score $R_{sys}(t)$. To keep the scenario realistic, we assume that $R_{sys}(t)$ changes across different operational phases as a result of Intrusion Detection systems (IDS) alerts or risk assessment inputs.

To investigate the application of the proposed framework on the two-tank system, we first present a step-by-step analysis in Subsection A, followed by an evaluation of the system

TABLE III
OPERATIONAL PHASES AND ASSOCIATED PARAMETERS

Phase	Description	AI Noise	H Noise	R_{sys}
Normal	Both agents receive accurate sensor readings.	0.00	0.00	0.50
Faulty	Sensor fault introduces noise into both agents' observations.	0.07	0.07	0.70
Post-Fault (Recovery 1)	Partial restoration of sensor fidelity.	0.03	0.03	0.65
Cyber Attack	Targeted attack degrades AI sensor data.	0.40	0.00	0.85
Post-Attack (Recovery 2)	System stabilizes under residual degradation.	0.08	0.00	0.75

behavior during each operational phase in Subsection B.

A. Framework implementation

MAP step: The two-tank system is modeled using the linearized plant matrices A , B , and C , which are provided in the MATLAB example². We do not repeat these matrices here due to space constraints; interested readers can find the full plant description and system performance in the referenced example. Building on this plant model, we extend the formulation to include separate control and observation pathways for the human and AI agents, as described in Equation (4). Both agents employ identical PID controllers ($K_p = 4.0$, $K_i = 0.8$, $K_d = 0.3$) and operate on potentially

²<https://se.mathworks.com/help/robust/ug/control-of-a-two-tank-system.html>

Fig. 3. Tanks Performance

different sensor measurements depending on the operational phase (see the noise levels for each agent in Table III). Using the linearized dynamics, we construct the controllability and observability matrices to perform a rank-based assessment of each agent’s control authority and perception capabilities.

MEASURE Step: The trust function is computed based on three main components, as explained in Equation (5). For simplicity, we assume that all parameters are weighted equally ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = 1/3$). In our case study, transparency $Tr(t)$ is assumed to be a constant value of 0.85, representing consistent system explainability. This aligns with real scenarios, as for instance an operator in OT domain uses Human Machine Interface (HMI) with predefined visual and information without the possibility of altering HMI drastically even if the operator needs that. In contrast, agreement $Ag(t)$ and reliability $Re(t)$ vary dynamically in practice. Agreement refers to the similarity between human and AI control actions. In our case study, we compute Agreement dynamically as $e^{-2 \cdot \text{control_difference}}$, using an exponential decay function. This formulation provides realistic modeling of action similarity and has been widely adopted in human-robot collaboration systems [28]. Reliability is set to 0.95 during the initial normal operation and then computed dynamically as $e^{-3 \cdot \text{AI_tracking_error}}$, based on AI tracking error. The exponential formulation offers a bounded and continuous assessment of system performance, which is established practice in control system evaluation [29], [30]. Exponential functions were chosen because they are commonly used in trust modeling due to their natural ability to capture gradual loss or recovery of trust [31]. Small deviations lead to minor changes, whereas larger errors result in steep trust reduction, reflecting how human trust typically reacts in real systems [32]. The coefficient values (2 for agreement, 3 for reliability) are calibrated based on empirical studies showing that humans are more sensitive to performance errors than to control disagreements [33], [34]. Figure 4 shows the measured trust components in different system operations.

The risk function is then computed using Equation (6). In this case study, we considered weights ($w_O = w_C = w_R = 1/3$). As explained in section III, $R_{sys}(t)$ is an external factor reflecting system risk score (see Table III). This is a realistic assumption, as other systems in OT environments, such as IDSs, might detect cyber attacks and trigger alerts, thereby increasing the risk level. Figure 5 illustrates the values of the trust and risk functions across different system operations.

MANAGE step: Based on the measured values and updated risk and trust functions in the previous step, the control authority is dynamically allocated using the adaptive delegation policy (control sharing in Equation (7)). Here we used the thresholds $\tau_{min} = 0.3$, $\tau_{max} = 0.7$, and $\rho_{safe} = 0.5$ for the case study. Figure 6 displays the dynamics of control authority between the human and AI across different system operation phases.

GOVERN step: Based on parameter sensitivity analysis, the governance layer was optimized with a window size of

Fig. 4. Trust components

Fig. 5. Trust and Risk Evolution

Fig. 6. Control Authority

$\Delta = 15$ timesteps, slope sensitivity $\varepsilon_s = 0.002$, variance threshold $\varepsilon_v = 0.005$, high trust threshold $\tau_H = 0.85$, and low trust threshold $\tau_L = 0.35$. These parameters enable reliable detection of trust modes and their transitions during system operation. It is worth noting that, to avoid overfitting, the same parameters were applied to four different types of attacks (not presented here due to page limitations). Table IV presents the classified trust modes for each operational phase. The GOVERN phase does not adapt parameters in real time. Instead, it logs trust modes, control authority, and risk values for later analysis. By reviewing these logs, especially during *Semi-Trusted (Degrading)* phases, it becomes possible to assess whether the trust evaluation fully aligns with the operational and security priorities of the OT domain. In realistic settings, this post-analysis can incorporate inputs from IDSs or other anomaly detection tools to confirm the occurrence of cyber attacks or hazardous conditions. The detailed analysis of these logs and how they influence parameter updates is discussed later in the GOVERN feedback section.

B. Result and analysis

In this subsection, we discuss the results for each operational phase, with the corresponding simulation outputs presented in Figures (3, 5, 4, and 6).

Phase 1 (Normal Operation): In the initial phase (0–20 s), both agents operate on accurate sensor readings with minimal noise (see Table III). As shown in Table IV, trust remains consistently high, with minimal slope variation and low variance, resulting in a Fully Trusted classification. Due to the stable environment, strong agreement between human and AI actions, and high reliability, the AI agent holds the control authority, as demonstrated in Figure 6, reflecting appropriate reliance under normal conditions.

Phase 2 (Faulty Sensors): A low-severity fault affects both human and AI sensors, introducing noise into the measurements (see Table III). This results in a modest drop in trust and a slight increase in risk. Trust exhibits a negative slope, reflecting reduced reliability caused by increased tracking errors and higher control disagreement in the trust function (see Figures 4 and 5). Consequently, α_{AI} decreases, and control authority shifts toward the human. The framework responds appropriately by reducing AI autonomy without abrupt overrides, thereby maintaining safe system performance. The GOVERN layer logs this phase as Semi-Trusted (Degrading), consistent with the observed

moderate trust levels and declining trend.

Phase 3 (Post-Fault (Recovery 1)): The sensor performance improves, allowing both agents to regain more accurate observations (see Table III). Agreement and reliability gradually recover, leading to an increase in trust with a positive slope. AI steadily regains control authority, demonstrating the framework’s ability to detect and respond to improving conditions without abrupt transitions or overreactions. As shown in Table IV, the trust mode for this phase is classified as Semi-Trusted (Recovering).

Phase 4 (Cyber attack): A simulated cyber attack introduces significant noise exclusively to the AI’s sensors, while the human agent remains unaffected. Trust in the AI drops sharply due to poor reliability and high disagreement. To realistically mimic the cyber attack, the $R_{sys}(t)$ score is increased to 0.8, reflecting security alert conditions in the OT environment. Consequently, α_{AI} decreases, and control authority shifts back to the human. This demonstrates the framework’s ability to detect untrustworthy conditions and dynamically revoke AI control. The trust mode for this phase is classified as Semi-Trusted (Degrading), as shown in Table IV. The analysis conducted in the GOVERN step, discussed later, further evaluates this classification and provides feedback to the framework, suggesting parameter updates to better align with OT security requirements.

Phase 5 (Post-Attack (Recovery 2)): We assume that the cyber attack is detected and subsides at the beginning of the Recovery 2 phase ($t = 80$). During phase 5, the AI’s sensor fidelity improves slightly but remains partially degraded, and the system risk score is slightly reduced (see Table III). As a result, trust begins to recover slowly (see Figure 5), showing a minimal positive slope, and the AI is gradually reintroduced into the control loop (see Figure 6), reflecting cautious re-engagement. This phase is correctly classified as Semi-Trusted (Recovering) in the trust mode, as presented in Table IV.

Analyzing all five phases shows that the proposed framework consistently classifies trust modes and adapts control authority proportionally across normal, faulty, attack, and recovery conditions. However, the GOVERN step not only logs these results but also offers an opportunity to assess whether the trust evaluation fully reflects the priorities of specific operational contexts. To demonstrate this capability of the GOVERN step, we next analyze the logs under an alternative assumption, treating the two-tank system as a critical OT plant with strict safety requirements, where reliability and human oversight are prioritized.

GOVERN feedback: As mentioned earlier, analyzing the logged in the GOVERN step suggests that the initial configuration classified trust modes reasonably and distributed control authority rationally. Nevertheless, to better explain

TABLE IV
STATE MODES ACROSS OPERATIONAL PHASES

Phase	Trust Mode	μ_T	$s_T(t)$	R_{sys}
Normal	Fully Trusted	0.916	0.0003	0.500
Faulty	Semi-Trusted (Degrading)	0.510	-0.0021	0.700
Recovery 1	Semi-Trusted (Recovering)	0.580	0.0005	0.651
Cyber Attack	Semi-Trusted (Degrading)	0.388	-0.0010	0.850
Recovery 2	Semi-Trusted (Recovering)	0.490	0.0005	0.750

the application of GOVERN step, here we assume that the plant conveys chemical liquid with strict safety requirements. In OT systems, particularly in high-risk domains (as in our example of a critical chemical plant), reliability is of utmost importance. This is reinforced by industrial standards such as NIST SP 800-82, ISA/IEC 62443, and ISO 13849, all of which emphasize that OT environments must ensure continuous, real-time operation, as any downtime or malfunction can lead to severe safety incidents, production losses, or environmental harm. In our framework, trust function is developed based on three factor namely transparency, agreement and reliability. Among these, reliability is the most decisive factor for safety, while transparency, as previously discussed, has limited variability in this context. Therefore, it is rational to adjust the trust weights to better emphasize reliability, making the framework more compliant with the security expectations in the particular plant under study. Based on this reasoning, we update the trust component weights to: $\lambda_1 = 0.2$ (transparency), $\lambda_2 = 0.3$ (agreement), and $\lambda_3 = 0.5$ (reliability). This adjustment reflects both the criticality of the plant and the principles of responsible AI, which emphasize human control and accountability in hazardous or uncertain conditions. Importantly, this is not a correction of an error, but an adaptive refinement derived from GOVERN’s compliance-oriented oversight.

Then we rerun the system with the updated weights. Table V shows the updated classification of trust mode and Figure 7 illustrates the updated control authority after the weight update. According to Table V, the cyber attack phase which previously classified as Semi-Trusted (Degrading), is now identified as Not Trusted, aligning more closely with OT safety requirements. Moreover, Figure 7 shows that control authority shifted more decisively toward the human during fault and cyber attack conditions, strengthening alignment with fail-safe principles in CPS and OT environments. The control authority plot in Figure 7 demonstrates that the GOVERN-driven weight adjustment leads to improved trust mode classification and control sharing that prioritizes safety. The human agent becomes the dominant controller in critical scenarios (faults and cyber attacks), while AI autonomy is restored only under safe conditions. This behavior confirms that GOVERN enhances system compliance with OT requirements and responsible AI principles.

Through this process, GOVERN demonstrates its supervisory function as logs are analyzed, areas where trust measurement can be better aligned with domain requirements are identified, and parameter refinements are suggested. This approach enhances interpretability and ensures that the framework remains compliant with trustworthy and responsible AI guidelines while meeting the stringent security and safety needs of critical OT systems.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we proposed TRA-HIC (Trust and Risk-Aware Human-AI Collaboration), a framework for human-AI collaboration in CPS/OT environments where operators work

TABLE V
STATE MODES ACROSS OPERATIONAL PHASES (AFTER GOVERN FEEDBACK)

Phase	Trust Mode	μ_T	$s_T(t)$	R_{sys}
Normal	Fully Trusted	0.930	0.0003	0.500
Faulty	Semi-Trusted (Degrading)	0.453	-0.0023	0.700
Recovery 1	Semi-Trusted (Recovering)	0.541	0.0006	0.651
Cyber Attack	Not Trusted	0.301	-0.0010	0.850
Recovery 2	Semi-Trusted (Recovering)	0.459	0.0006	0.750

Fig. 7. Control Authority

alongside AI-enabled systems. Our framework is structured in four steps, inspired by the NIST AI Risk Management Framework, and incorporates trustworthy AI principles with an emphasis on human-centric AI, particularly for critical systems. The proposed framework (i) models humans and AI as co-controllers with explicit observability and controllability metrics, (ii) incorporates trust calibration and state transitions, (iii) enables risk-aware control redistribution, and (iv) aligns with the NIST AI RMF. The framework has been applied to a standard use case from the control theory domain to showcase its operation. It provides valuable insights into the interaction between the human and AI controllers, resulting in a more detailed and robust understanding of when and how control parameters shall be adapted and the control shall be shifted between the human and AI controllers.

It is important to acknowledge that the trust states defined in this framework are based on a simplified quantitative model of trust dynamics, primarily driven by observable system metrics (e.g., transparency, agreement, reliability). Moreover, in our paper, such dynamics are reflected in the selection of values $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, w_O, w_C$ and w_R for the metrics. In terms of future work, we intend to further develop our approach for the selection of these metrics for the proposed framework. The goal would be to support the application of the framework for use cases in different domains with varying levels of criticality, by providing a systematic way to define the corresponding parameter values.

While our trust function is built on three metrics commonly represented in recent research works and guidelines, in practice, human trust is influenced by a range of cognitive, contextual, and individual factors, such as prior experience, fatigue, personality, and organizational culture. Additionally, different operators working in shifts may exhibit different baseline trust levels toward the same AI behavior, affecting how the system is used or overridden. In future work, we plan to explore an extended range of metrics that may affect human-AI collaboration, particularly in the OT domain. We also intend to validate the usefulness of the model by presenting its operation to different stakeholders and applying it to various use cases. Stakeholders input on the application of our methodology will provide valuable feedback and allow us to calibrate human to AI trust in different scenarios.

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